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INDEPENDENCE OF HOME CARE NURSING IN THE OPINION OF PERSONS USING THIS FORM OF HEALTH CARE SERVICES

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Summary and conclusions

Registered nurses carrying out health services at patients' homes should assure a sense of security for the sick persons and their families/carers by establishing and maintaining the verbal and non-verbal communication, among others [1, 3, 4, 9, 11].

The performed study demonstrates that the patients in both compared groups have been assured a sense of security.

The process of nursing the surveyed patients provided with home care conducted by nurses is also supposed to encompass health care education elements associated with teaching the rules of regular feeding, managing in situations of limited self-service, legitimacy of the use of orthopedic supply and its adjustment to the patients' health expectations.

Both of the surveyed groups replied similarly that the nursing care performed at home is a better form of nursing than the treatment in a specialist clinic involving everyday journeys. Chronic and disabled patients very frequently have big problems with organizing the journey to a specialist clinic. If they manage to successfully fix the journey, later on they are nervous whether they will be able to take care of all the formalities, waiting for their turn. This nervous tension repeatedly blurs the results of blood pressure tests and may also cause a disturbed motor coordination, altered visual and auditory perception, and psychological discomfort.

The demand for long-term home care among elderly, chronically ill and disabled people is growing bigger and will grow further because of the issue of the ageing of the society. It is considered that in the near future long-term home care should develop more and more dynamically to fulfill the needs of the people in old age and with lowered psychophysical fitness. This form of care is most desirable for people who cannot or do not agree to leave their homes and move to the institutional care. Leaving the aged, chronic and disabled people at their own homes, their state of health permitting, is definitely a better solution.

The research suggests that long-term home care lowers the number of visits of a family doctor or a specialist, as well as the times an ambulance was called to a patient's home during the last year.

These results indicate the improvement in the quality of life of persons provided with long-term home care. The main reasons for which the patient is satisfied with the quality of his life are the following: (1) perceptible improvement in health noticed by the family, (2) acceptance of their state of health, (3) a feeling of being needed by the family, (4) the possibility of relying on the nurse, (5) better mental state, and (6) improved physical fitness. The nurses working at the patient's home reduce the costs related to the treatment of patients in geriatric age and enhance the access to health services for people receiving a modest salary and the disabled.

Introduction

The Central Statistical Office (GUS) forecasts an appreciable increase in percentage of elderly people in seaside provinces. One also expects big changes going in the direction of evening out the percentage of elderly people in the populations of all provinces of our country. It is predicted that in 2030 the proportion of aged people will be the lowest in the Podkarpackie province. On the other hand, the largest proportion of people in geriatric age will live in the central provinces such as the Mazovian, Świętokrzyskie, Łódzkie, Silesian and Opolskie provinces.

As a result of this situation the division observed since the end of World War II into demographically "young" western and northern provinces that were settled with young incoming population and the "old" eastern provinces observed in Poland will change profoundly.

The long-term home care is a relatively new field of nursing that is carried out at the level of basic health care.

This form of nursing is directed to chronic and disabled persons who are most frequently in geriatric age, in situations requiring systematic and specialist care but with the possibility of performing it at the patient's home.

The long-term home care is directed to persons displaying large health deficits such as chronic diseases (multiple diseases), physical and mental disability, lack of independence in self-care and self-nursing, terminal states, neoplastic diseases, and vegetative states (coma).

The realization of health services in long-term home care is performed by graduate nurses who finished their specialization in long-term home care; nurses specialized in community and family care or geriatric nursing. It is also performed by people who finished a qualifying course in the long-term care or a course for chronic and disabled persons.

Graduate nurses are sufficiently prepared to carry out health services at a patient's home.

The work of nurses at home environment is directed to persons receiving health services and is dictated by the market of health services.

The independence of work carried out by nurses in the course of long-term home care results in increased availability of appropriate health services for people with health problems

This work aims to show the usefulness of functioning of the home care provided by the nurses and legitimacy of increasing financial outlays for this form of health care in the community of chronic and disabled persons.

The subject matter and research methods

The study was performed on a randomly chosen sample of 300 patients in total obtaining long-term home care who lived in Lublin and Silesian provinces. Out of the total number of the surveyed individuals, 243 persons actually provided answers. Both groups consisted of people in geriatric age, chronically ill and disabled and thus depended on others.

Methods employed in our study are as follows: (1) the standardized WHOQOL - Bref questionnaire, (2) an original questionnaire based on an established pattern of long-term home care realized, (3) Barthel's scale, and (4) Douglas' scale.

Research findings and comments

A straight majority of the respondents reported an improvement in their quality of life since providing them with long-term home care - 91.20% of positive responses the Silesian province and 96.61% in the Lublin province. The negative responses amounted to 8.80% and 3.39%, respectively. The percentage distribution of responses in both of the compared groups was similar. There was no statistically significant correlation at an error level of under 5% (Table 1).

Table 1. The improvement of life comfort experienced by patients since they started being provided with long-term home care

	Lublin province		Silesian province	
	No.	%	No.	%
No	11	8.80	114	8.80
Total	125	100.00	118	100.00
χ^2	1.221			
p	NS			

The patients gave the following reasons of improving their comfort of life since receiving the long-term home care: the possibility of nursing at home (30.38% of patients from the Silesian province and 24.31% from the Lublin province), assurance of a sense of security (20.25% and 25.88%, respectively), permanent nursing (20.89% and 20.39%). Convenient times of home visits were indicated more rarely (5.70% and 9.41%). The percentage distribution of answers was similar in both compared groups ($P > 0.05$) (Table 2).

Table 2. Reasons why patients believe their comfort of life has improved since they were provided with long-term home care by a nurse

	Silesian province		Lublin province	
	No.*	%	No.*	%
Permanent and continuous nursing	33	20.89	52	20.39
The nurse being systematic	36	22.78	51	20.00
The possibility of being nursed at home	48	30.38	62	24.31
The patient sets a convenient time of the nurse's visit	9	5.70	24	9.41
The assurance of a sense of security	32	20.25	66	25.88
Total	125	100.00	203	100.00
χ^2	1.221			
p	NS			

* Multiple choice questions

The responses to the question why long-term home care is better than regular travels to a specialist clinic (Table 3). The conducted comparative analysis did not demonstrate any statistically significant correlation at an error level not lower than 5%.

Table 3. Reasons for which the patient feels that the care of the nurse providing long-term home care is better than undergoing procedures in a specialist clinic with regular travels

	Silesian province		Lublin province	
	No.	%	No.	%
Transport costs	16	11.43	25	14.45
Involving the family/carers	32	22.86	34	19.65
Waiting in a queue	22	15.71	28	16.18
Adjusting to a set time of an appointment	24	17.14	28	16.18
Getting nervous/stressed	26	18.57	32	18.50
Distorted sense of security	20	14.29	26	15.03

Total	124	100.00	148	100.00
χ^2	0.545			
p	NS			

Health care service provided by a nurse at a patient's home helps decrease the number of visits of a family doctor, a medical specialist and distinctly diminishes the number of calling an ambulance.

The respondents from both provinces agree that since the moment of providing them with long-term home care the visits of the family doctor are rare.

In the Silesian province the percentage of patients maintaining that a family doctor was called frequently amounted to 17.60% while in the Lublin province it was only 7.63% (Table 4). The difference in the percentage distribution of responses received in two compared provinces indicates a statistically significant correlation ($p < 0.05$).

Table 4. Calling a family doctor for a home visit since covering a patient with long-term home care

	Silesian province		Lublin province	
	No.	%	No.	%
Frequently	22	17.60	9	7.63
Rarely	103	82.40	109	92.37
Total	125	100.00	118	100.00
χ^2	4.554			
p	<0.05			

Table 5. Number of home visits carried out by a family doctor during one year since the moment of providing patients with long-term care

	Silesian province		Lublin province	
	No.	%	No.	%
Above 10	16	12.80	5	4.24
5-10	25	20.00	17	14.41
Below 5	84	67.20	96	81.36
Total	125	100.00	118	100.00
χ^2	3.121			
p	<0.05			

The respondents from the Silesian province were visited by a family doctor more frequently than those from the Lublin province since being provided with long-term home care (correlation at a confidence level of above 95%). As many as 81.36% of respondents of the Lublin province declared that the doctor was called less than 5 last year, 14.41% - 5 to 10 times, and only 4.24% over 10 times last year. With regards to the respondents in the Silesian province these percentages were 67.20%, 20.00% and 12.80%, respectively (Table 5).

Since covering patients with long-term home care, the number of visits of a specialist doctor at respondents' homes in the Lublin province was lower than that in the Silesian province. 66.10% of respondents from the Lublin province stated that there were no visits of a specialist, 33.05% - that there were no more than 5 visits and 0.85% said that their number was above 5. The percentage distribution among the respondents in the Silesian province was as follows: 59.20%, 29.60% and 11.20%, respectively (Table 6).

Table 6. Number of home visits carried out by a specialist doctor during one year from the moment of covering patients with long-term care

	Silesian province		Lublin province	
	No.	%	No.	%
More than 5	14	11.20	1	0.85
1-5	37	29.60	39	33.05
None	74	59.20	78	66.10
Total	125	100.00	118	100.00
χ^2	4.820			
p	<0.05			

Only 6.40% of the respondents from the Silesian province and 8.47% from the Lublin province called an ambulance more than 3 times from the moment of including them in the long-time home care scheme. During this same period 28.00% and 17.80% of respondents, correspondingly, called an ambulance from 1 to 3 times (Table 7). The remaining respondents never called an ambulance during the last year. The conducted statistical analysis indicates a statistically significant correlation at a level of over 95% between the two groups of patients.

Table 7. Number of calls to an emergency ambulance service since the beginning of providing patients with long-term home care

	Silesian province		Lublin province	
	No.	%	No.	%
Over 3 times	8	6.40	10	8.47
No more than 3 times	35	28.00	21	17.80
None	82	65.60	87	73.73
Total	125	100.00	118	100.00
χ^2	3.265			
p	<0.05			

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